

Morphology and electrokinetic behavior of styrene-2-ethylhexyl acrylate copolymer latex for coatings prepared by two-stage seeded emulsion polymerization

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The styrene (ST)-2-methylhexyl acrylate (EHA) copolymer latexes were synthesized through two-stage seeded emulsion polymerization (TSSEP) technique which were compared with the conventional emulsion polymerization (CEP) technique. The morphologies, particle size and electrokinetic behaviors of TSSEP and CEP latexes were studied through transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and Zetasizer respectively. It was found that the latex particles of TSSEP were all uniform and almost spherical in morphology. The particle size as well as polydispersity of TSSEP latex was smaller than that of CEP latex, and the particle size measurement of TEM corresponded with that of Zetasizer. Electrokinetic studies showed that all latexes were negative systems, and the particles exhibited colloidal stability under basic conditions. The negative value of ζ -potential for TSSEP latex was larger than that for CEP latex over the whole range of measured pH and NaCl concentrations, i.e. TSSEP latex demonstrated higher electrostatic stability than CEP latex. The ζ -potential reached the maximum value at approximately 3×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of NaCl concentration indicating the highest colloidal stability of TSSEP and CEP latexes. At very high salt concentration ([NaCl] = 0.1 M), we obtained very small ζ -potential values, thus the colloidal stability of ST-EHA copolymer latexes was much low.

Styrene (ST)-acrylate copolymer latexes are widely used as binders of paper coatings, building coatings and textile coatings¹⁻⁴. There are a number of studies on the seeded emulsion polymerization of ST-acrylate concerning its uniform particle size, thermal stability, electrochemical stability, excellent binding ability and other properties⁵⁻⁹. So far, very few investigations on the seeded emulsion polymerization of ST-2-ethylhexyl acrylate (EHA) copolymer latex have been done. Considering the similarity of EHA to BA, many references about ST-BA copolymer latex have been quoted in this paper. In order to obtain core-shell polymer emulsion of uniform particle size, the two-stage seeded emulsion polymerization (TSSEP) is usually performed^{10,11}. Under some circumstances, the morphology and electrokinetics of latex particles can account for the mechanism of the seeded emulsion polymerization and the latex stability.

The morphology of the copolymer latex particle is largely influenced by two important factors¹². One factor is the relative hydrophilicity of the different phases in the particle, which can be controlled by choosing monomers of different hydrophilicity. When hydrophilic monomers such as acrylic acid (AA) are used, the influence of terminal initiator end groups on the morphology can be neglected. An-

other important parameter for the morphology development is the particle viscosity. The thermodynamically favored morphology can be gained with a low internal particle viscosity. Chu and Guyot¹³ studied the latex morphology including particle size distributions in multisized emulsion copolymerization of ST, butyl acrylate (BA) and methacrylic acid (MAA) by means of two-stage polymerization techniques. They proposed that the high solid content, the good film-forming characteristics and the improved mechanical and rheological properties could be obtained with multisized polymer emulsion being of considerable industrial interest and importance.

The polymer latex in water may be regarded as the model system for the interaction potential of the particles^{14,15}. Generally, the aqueous latex particles are mainly electrostatically stabilized through chemically bound or adsorbed charges, and purely sterically stabilized latex where the stabilization is achieved only through polymer chains affixed to the surface has been seldom found. Shirahama and Suzawa¹⁶ investigated the electrokinetics of ST/2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (PHEMA) copolymer latex. They reported that the pH dependence of surface charges for the latex was not very pronounced, but the negative values of ζ -potentials for PS/PHEMA latex were smaller than

that for PS latex over the whole range of measured pH. In other words, the electrochemical stability of PS/PHEMA latex was lower than that of PS latex.

In the present article we report on the morphology and electrokinetics of ST-2-ethylhexyl acrylate (EHA) copolymer latex prepared by TSSEP compared with the conventional emulsion polymerization (CEP). From the studies on morphology and electrokinetic behavior of the latex particles, a lot of information about the latex stability, the latex property and the polymerization mechanism can be obtained.

Experimental

Materials : Styrene (ST), 2-ethylhexyl acrylate (EHA), acrylic acid (AA) and ethoxylated nonyl phenol containing ten units of ethylene oxide (OP10) were of industrial grade, and used as supplied. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), ammonium persulfate (AP) and ammonia water ($\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) were chemically pure. All other chemicals were of analytical grade.

Preparation of conventional copolymer latexes : CEP was carried out in a stirred 500 ml reactor fitted with an overhead condenser and two feed funnels. The amounts of surfactants (OP and SDS) were twice of that in the seeded polymerization, and the same monomer-initiator composition as in the seeded polymerization was used (see Table 1). The temperature of the reactor contents was maintained at 40–80°C by partially immersing the reactor in a thermostated water bath. The starting materials, consisting of 1/4 of mixed monomers (ST, EHA and AA), surfactants (OP10 and SDS) and deionized water, were stirred for 0.5 h and the temperature was set at 40°C. Then the starting materials were heated to 80°C, AP and the other 3/4 mixed monomers were fed from two funnels simultaneously in 2 h. After the total addition, the reaction mixture was heated for an additional 2 h at 82°C. While stirring, the temperature was lowered to 50°C, and the mixture neutralized to pH value 8–9 by $\text{NH}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Finally the reaction mixture was filtered at 40°C.

Preparation of two-stage seeded copolymer latexes : Seed latexes were prepared through semicontinuous copolymerization in a 500 ml glass reactor. The starting materi-

als included four components A, B, C and D, a typical recipe is given in Table 1. The reactor was repeatedly degassed and purged with the nitrogen, and 120 g deionized water was added. When it was tempered at 90°C, 80 g component C was charged, and the temperature decreased. The component A and the remaining component C were drop-fed into the reactor from two funnels simultaneously for 2 h at 86°C, then the reaction mixture was heated for an additional 0.5 h at 88°C. The seed latexes were used without further treatment in the second polymerization stage.

The second-stage polymerization was carried out in a 1-L glass reactor, its typical recipe is also given in Table 1. The seed latexes were charged into the second-stage reactor. Then the temperature was raised to 85°C, the components B and D were drop-fed into the reactor from two funnels simultaneously for 1.5 h, and the temperature was maintained at 86°C for another 1.5 h. AP was added into the reactor at 50°C. Finally, the core-shell latexes of ST-EHA copolymers were filtered at 40°C.

Morphology of latexes : The morphology of latex particles was observed under Hitachi-H800 transmission electron microscopy (TEM) at 75 kV. The emulsion samples was directly applied to the copper grid covered with a collodion film, and the cast film was stained with uranyl acetate solution.

Particle size of latexes : The average size of latex particles and their size distribution were determined by use of Zetasizer 1000/3000. The latex samples were usually dispersed by ultrasonic agitation before size measurements, and the maximum concentration of latexes for measurements was set at 0.1 g dm^{-3} . The samples were diluted to a certain solid content by demineralised water with a small amount of salt added, e.g. 1 millimolar NaCl, and this ensured that an extended electric double layer doesn't artificially increase the size by a few nanometers. The count rate was in the range 50–200 Kcp (1000 per second). The particle size was also measured from TEM photos by taking the average of 50 latex particles at random.

Zeta (ζ)-potentials of latexes : Zeta (ζ)-potentials were mainly studied in the electrokinetic behavior of ST-EHA copolymer latexes with the aid of Zetasizer 2000/3000. The latex samples were usually dispersed by ultrasonic agita-

Table 1. Recipes of two-stage seed emulsion polymerization

Components	ST (g)	EHA (g)	AA (g)	SDS (g)	OP10 (g)	AP (g)	NaHCO_3 (g)	H_2O (g)
A	104.8	57.6	4.8	–	–	–	–	–
B	84.8	114.4	4.8	–	–	–	–	–
C	–	–	–	1.6	4.0	1.6	1.0	256.0
D	–	–	–	–	–	1.2	1.0	32.0

tion before ζ -potential measurements. The concentrations of latex samples were set at 0.05 g dm^{-3} . ζ -potential was measured as a function of pH or electrolyte concentration by calculating the average of five measurements at the stationary level in a cylindrical cell. The pH or ionic strength was adjusted with HCl, NaOH and NaCl solutions.

Results and discussion

Morphology of latexes : The morphologies of latex particles prepared through TSSEP and CEP were observed under TEM, see Figs. 1(a) and (b). The magnification multiples of the photograph (a) and (b) were 20000 and 4000 respectively. From Fig. 1(a), it was shown that the latex particles of TSSEP were all uniform in morphology, and the particles were almost spherical. Fig. 1(b) displayed that the latex particles of CEP were not regular in morphology and not uniform in size, i.e. the particles were multidispersed^{17,18}. When the latex particles coalesced to form a film, the TSSEP latex formed a transparent film with monophasic morphology, whereas a white film with multiphase morphology was obtained with CEP. Obviously, the latex morphologies under TEM closely agreed with the corresponding films.

Fig. 1. TEM micrographs of latex particles after the copolymerization of ST-EHA : (a) TSSEP latex particles, (b) CEP latex particles.

Particle size of latexes : The latex particle size of TSSEP or CEP were measured through Zetasizer 1000/3000, and the sample concentration was set at 0.1 g dm^{-3} . Figs. 2 and 3 showed the measured results of TSSEP and CEP latexes individually. The average size of TSSEP latex particles was 119.0 nm and the particle size distribution was relatively narrow, while the average size of CEP latex particles was 260.0 nm with the bimodal size distribution. It was clear that the particle size polydispersity of TSSEP was smaller than that of CEP.

In this work, the average particle size of TSSEP latex had also been determined under TEM by taking the aver-

Fig. 2. The particle size distribution of TSSEP latex at 25°C. Latex concentration 0.1 g dm^{-3} .

Fig. 3. The particle size distribution of CEP latex at 25°C. Latex concentration 0.1 g dm^{-3} .

age of 50 spherical particles from Fig. 1(a), which was approximately 120 nm. Therefore, the particle size measurement of TEM corresponded with that of Zetasizer. However, the average particle size of CEP latex could not be measured from Fig. 1(b), because the CEP latex particles were not uniform in size and not regular in morphology as described above.

In TSSEP, stable and uniform seed particles were first obtained from the first-stage copolymerization, and the surfactant layers (SDS and OP-10) covered on the surface of seed particle (i.e. the core). During the second-stage of reaction, the surfactants were not added again, and the second-stage monomers associated with the surfactants on the seed surface copolymerize with each other gradually under the similar reaction conditions to the first stage. Thus, the shell thickness of particles due to the second stage reaction didn't diversify much, and uniform and spherical particles

formed. But in CEP, the reaction temperature was lower, the surfactant concentration and especially the monomer concentration were higher than that in first stage reaction of TSSEP during the same reaction time. It is well known^{10,11} that the mechanism of nucleation is greatly influenced by temperature and monomer concentration. When the reaction temperature was lower, the initiator AP would dissociate to release fewer free radicals, smaller number of particles would be generated, and under the same monomer concentration the particle size would be larger. The particle size will also be larger if the monomer concentration is higher, since smaller copolymer particles have more opportunities to coalesce into larger particles. According to CHU¹³, the increased amount of surfactants usually causes the diversity of latex particles, and this increases the irregularity of the particle morphology. Therefore, the particle size of CEP latex was larger, and its distribution was wider.

Electrokinetics of latexes: As we know, the electrostatic stability of a colloid system increases with the increase of ζ -potential value (meaning the larger electrostatic repulsion of colloid particles) in the light of DLVO theory. The ζ -potential values for TSSEP and CEP latexes were measured as functions of pH at a constant ionic strength of 0.001 M NaCl and of NaCl concentrations to characterize the electric double layer surrounding the colloid particles¹⁹. The results given in Figs. 4 and 5 showed that all studied latexes were negative systems.

From Fig. 4, it can be seen that the negative value of ζ -potential for TSSEP latex was larger than that for CEP latex over the whole range of measured pH. This result illustrated that TSSEP latex was more electrostatically stable than CEP latex for the reason of the regular electrical double layer of TSSEP latex according to the uniformity of the particles and the irregular electrical double layer of CEP latex due to the unevenness of the particles. From pH =

Fig. 4. ζ -Potentials of TSSEP and CEP latexes as a function of pH. [NaCl] = 1 mmol dm⁻³].

3.00 to 9.00 or so, ζ -potentials for both latexes increased with the higher pH values, because COOH groups in lower pH value dissociated into COO⁻ ions in higher pH values to increase the negative charge of the electric double layer. Whereas ζ -potentials were constant when pH values were larger than 9.00 meaning that the negative charges in the electric double layer did not vary. The electrokinetic behaviors of these latexes indicated that the particles could be more colloidal stable under basic conditions.

Fig. 5. ζ -Potentials of TSSEP and CEP latexes as a function NaCl concentration at 25°C.

As observed in Fig. 5, ζ -potentials of TSSEP latexes were larger than that of CEP latexes (just as same as the results shown in Fig. 4). It was notable that the ζ -potential reached the maximum value at approximately 3×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of NaCl concentration indicating the highest electrostatic stability of TSSEP and CEP latexes. According to DLVO theory, a reasonable explanation for the increase in ζ -potential till 3×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of NaCl concentration is the adsorption of negative chloride ions to the surface of latex particles from the diluted latex solution. ζ -Potential decreased above this NaCl concentration due to the compression of the electrical double layer and the screening effect of the latex polyelectrolyte charges by the excessive salt ions²⁰. At very high salt concentration ([NaCl] = 0.1 M), we obtained very small ζ -potential values, thus the colloidal stability of ST-EHA copolymer latexes was much low.

Conclusions: It was found that the latex particles of TSSEP were all uniform in morphology, and the particles were almost spherical. The average size of TSSEP latex particles was 119.0 nm and the particle size distribution was relatively narrow, while the average size of CEP latex particles was 260.0 nm with the bimodal size distribution. Therefore, the particle size polydispersity of TSSEP latex was smaller than that of CEP latex. In addition, the average particle size of TSSEP latex determined under TEM corres-

ponded with that of Zetasizer. From the electrokinetic behaviors of latexes, it was apparent that TSSEP latex was more electrostatically stable than CEP latex, and the colloidal stability of ST-EHA copolymer latexes was much low at very high salt concentration.

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